

Physiological disorders of Cauliflower causes and Management.

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Abstract:

Physiological disorders are abnormalities in plants which are associated to non pathogenic factors. A plant or its part may show unusual growth. function such abnormalities are widely referred to as disorders. These may incited by nutrients deficiency or excess, hormonal imbalance, abnormal growing conditions etc physiological disorders are one of the major which cause economic losses worldwide (Mishra et al, 2016). Physiological disorders can be termed as the abnormalities that can be seen in leaf, stem and fruit morphology, colour, or both which are not caused by infectious diseases or insects. These abnormalities occur due to adverse environment conditions and inadequate amount of nutrients in the plant. Brassica vegetables contain low fat, high vitamin, mineral and fibre as well as various phytochemicals (Sanlier N and Guler Saban M 2018). Among of all Cauliflower is one of the major cole crops grown in the world. As a vegetable it provides leaves, stem, flower and roots that are consumed freshly or by processing. It has high amount of nutrients and vitamins. This crop is grown in wide variety of soils and in all seasons. Cauliflower is sensitive to a number of disorders which reduce the quality and yield of the produce (Hazra and Som, 1999). Being a thermo-sensitive crop with the temperature fluctuation disorder will found in a crop and finally yield of the crop will reduces. The major disorder of cauliflower are riceyness, blindness, leafiness or bracting, pinking, multiple curds, browning, chlorosis, whip tail, tip burn, buttoning, hollow stem, fuzzy curd and black speck.

Keywords: cauliflower, cole crops, thermo-sensitive, physiological disorders

Introduction:

Cauliflower is one of the most important winter vegetables grow in India. It is a European origin, probably develop from broccoli. In India, cauliflower farming is done in almost all the states, but the main states are Bihar, U. P., Orissa, Assam, M.P., Gujarat, and Haryana. Cauliflower (*Brassica oleraceae* var. *Botrytis*) is most important winter season vegetable crops and it belong to the family cruciferae. It is cultivated for its tender and snow white to yellowish curd. It is utilized for pickles, soups and curries. It is opulent in carbohydrates, vitamins A, C and minerals. Cauliflower thrives best in a cool moist climate. It does not withstand very low temperature or an inordinate amount of heat. Cauliflower curd will not develop well in sultry weather, for this reason it is grown in winte. The optimum temperature range of cauliflower is 10 to 15⁰ C. In region where freeze does not occur, planting may be done at any time of the year if dihydrogen monoxide is available for growing the crop. In regions where hard freezes occur well-hardened plants may be set out as early in the spring (Rahman *et al*, 2007).

The plants may fail to compose desirable curd in dry and sultry weather which causes the curd to develop prematurely and bolt or button. It requires moderately cool climates during the period of its magnification (Singh *et al*, 2019). Physiological plant disorders caused by non-pathological disorders like poor light intensity, weather injury, water-logging or an absence of nutrients, and have an effect on the functioning of the system. Physiological disorder is distinguished from disease caused by microorganism, like a virulent disease or plant (Sharma, 2016). The

symptoms of physiological disorders might seem disease-like, they'll sometimes be prevented by sterilization environmental conditions. However, once a plant shows symptoms of nutrient deficiency it's doubtless "y are reduced. Any reasonably abnormality in economically necessary part of vegetables or different components that contribute to yield and quality of vegetable is termed as physiological disorder

Causes of physiological disorder: The causes of physiological disorders are

1. Sudden fluctuation in temperature
2. Deficiency of nutrient
3. Improper moisture availability during cultivation

Cauliflower suffers from a number of physiological disorders, which manifest in different type of disease syndromes. Some physiological disorders depend mainly on hereditary factor, whereas, other are fluctuation occurring in temperature, air, water, humidity, organic and inorganic nutrition. Important physiological disorders, affecting cauliflower are described below:

Riceyness:

It manifests in the elongation on peduncle wearing flower buds, rendering curds, granular, loose and somewhat velvety. A premature initiation of floral bud is characterized by riceyness in cauliflower and is considered to be of poor quality for marketing. At IARI, New Delhi, it has been found that this disorder may result from any temperature higher or lower than the optimum required for particular cultivars. Riceyness mainly and harvesting has been delayed. If late variety planted early, riceyness develops due to the prevalent of high temperature, however, if can also

appear at lower temperature. Hereditary factors have also been reported for riceyness. Heavy dose of nitrogen and high relative humidity also contributes to riceyness. Due to fluctuations in temperature and poor seed stock this disorder occurs (Grevsen *et al*, 2003) It can be controlled by cultivation of genetically pure seed and appropriate varieties with recommended cultural practices. It can be controlled by cultivation of genetically pure seed and appropriate varieties with recommended cultural practices. Harvest while the curd is still firm, compact, white and fairly smooth; if it gets too mature, it will become grainy or ricey. Proper management of soil moisture and fertility during the development of head or curd.

Fuzziness:

It appears as the flower pedicels of velvety curds elongate. The anomaly is both hereditary and non-hereditary. Cultivation of cauliflower, out of their normal season encourages fuzziness. This is caused to hereditary or due to unfavourable conditions (Boersma *et al*, 2013). Sowing good quality seed in right season under proper cultural practices minimizes fuzziness.

Leafiness:

This disorder is commonly seen by formation of small thin leaves from the curd which reduces quality of curd. Extremely small green leaves appear in between the curd segment due to inheritable or non-heritable factors. Prevalence of high temperatures during curding phase aggravates leafiness. This is caused due to high temperature after curdling stage and delay in harvesting. Certain varieties are more sensitive to leafiness or bracketing than other. It can be controlled by selection of varieties according to their adaptability.

Browning (Brown Rot or Red Rot):

It is caused by boron deficiency which is influenced by soil pH. The availability of boron decreases at neutral soil reaction. It is characterized by sign on the young leaves that become dark green and brittle. The old leaves pucker, chlorotic and often drop off. Sometimes, the downward curling of older leaves followed by development of blisters when boron deficiency is severe. The leaves remain small and the growing point may die. However, in later stage, water soaked, light brown to dark brown spots formed on the stem and branches may ultimately lead to the formation of cavities formed on the stem and branches may ultimately lead to the formation of cavities and a hollow stem. Curds may also show irregular water soaked spots. Which alter change to a rusty brown colour. The affected curds remain small and acquire a bitter taste. This may be controlled by application of borax or sodium borate or sodium tetra borate at the rate of 20 kg/ha a soil application. In case of acute deficiency, spray of 0.25 to 0.50 per cent solution of borax at the rate of 1 to 2 kg/ha depending upon growth, soil reaction

and extent of deficiency. Spraying of 0.2 to 0.25 % boric acid or sodium borate is equally effective (Hazra and Som, 1999).

Whiptail:

Deficiency of molybdenum causes 'whiptail' syndrome, especially, in highly acidic soils. Because high manganese concentrations in such soils hinder the uptake of molybdenum which seldom occurs when the soil pH is 5.5 or higher. The young cauliflower plants become chlorotic and may turn white, particularly along the leaf margins. In young plants chlorosis of leaf margins can be seen and whole leaves turn white (Swati, 2015). They also become cupped and wither. The leaves blades fail to develop properly, and the leaves are ruffled and distorted. In older plant, the lamina of the newly formed leaves are irregular in shape, frequently, consisting of only a large bare midrib and hence, the common name "whiptail". It can be corrected by application of lime or dolomite limestone to raise the soil pH up to 6.5 or higher. Sodium or Ammonium molybdate at the rate of 1-2 kg/ha as soil application can also control "whiptail" of cauliflower.

Buttoning:

In the early stages of plant growth after formation of few number of leaves development of small white coloured buttons or curds can be seen. There are several factors causes buttoning of cauliflower like deficiency of nitrogenous fertilizers, planting of over aged seedlings because aged seedlings after establishment do not get sufficient time to initiate growth before curding, planting of early variety late and exposure of the transplants to poor light conditions. This disorder can be controlled by application of excess doses of nitrogen; minimization of transplantation shocks and provides favourable conditions during the vegetative growth of plant and the seedlings to be transplanted should not be more than six weeks (Wurr *et al*, 1984)

Blindness:

Plant without terminal bud. Collapse of growing point. No curd formation. The leaves become thick, dark green, large and leathery by accumulating carbohydrates and the plant remains vegetative (Kalisza *et al*, 2018). This is due to low temperature and insects such as cutworms. This can be controlled by application of insecticides which kills the insects and prevent the buds being damaged and avoid exposure to low temperature.

Tip burn:

Tissues around the leaf margin gradually dry and give a papery texture. In severe cases the leaves become necrotic and deformed. Tipburn incidence can be modified by several environmental factors including temperature, relative humidity, soil moisture and soil fertility (Nieuwhof, 1960). Increasing the air temperature, lack of soil moisture, or excessive soil moisture tend to enhance tipburn

incidence. One common characteristic of tipburn is that occurrence is usually greatest in young, rapidly growing leaf tissue, particularly during curd enlargement. High rates of N fertilizer have been reported to increase incidence and or severity of tipburn in cauliflower (Jenkinson and Campbell, 1957).

References:

1. Kumar, M. and Sen, N.L. 2005. Effect of zinc, boron and gibberellic acid on yield of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.) Moench). *Indian J. Hort.* 62 (3): 308- 309.
2. Boersma, M., Gracie, A. J., & Brown, P. H. (2013). Evidence of mechanical tissue strain in the development of hollow stem in broccoli. *Scientia horticulturae*, 164, 353-358.
3. Bose, T.K., J Kabir, Maity, T.K & Parathasarathy, Som M.G
4. Grevsen, K., Olesen, J. E., & Veierskov, B. (2003). The effects of temperature and plant developmental stage on the occurrence of the curd quality defects and riceness in cauliflower *The Journal of Horticultural Science and Biotechnology*, 78(5), 638-646.
5. Hazra, P., & Som M.G. (1999). Technology for vegetable production and improvement, Naya Prakash 1(185-188).
6. Kalise., A. Sekara, Cebula, S., Graowska, A., & Kunicki, E (2014) Impact of low temperature transplant treatment on yield and quality of cauliflower curds in late spring production. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 176, 134-142.
7. Sharma, N., Kumar, A., Kumar, V., Kumar, M., Jamwal, A., Singh, S., Jamwal, S., Rai, A.P., Khajuria, S. and Arora, R. (2016). Physiological disorders in solanaceous and bulb crops: a review. *International journal of agricultural sciences*, 8, (52) pp.-2566-2568.
8. Singh, A., Singh, A., Shekhar, R., P, S, R., & Sing, D K. (2019). The response of cauliflower var. Snowball affected by different day stages level and spacing distances. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, SP3:04-07
9. Wurr, D. C. E., & Fellows, J. R. (1984). Cauliflower buttoning the role of transplant size. *Journal of horticultural science*, 59(3), 419-42
10. Cauliflower Cultivation Guide (2024) (agricultureguruji.com)